

HUMAN INFLUENCE ON NATURE AND ECOLOGY

Madinakhon Alimova Iskandar kizi

“TIAME” NRU researcheradmin

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8306049>

Abstract. *Based on the requirements of the time and the needs of humanity, the ideas and opinions about the impact of human actions on nature and ecology were aimed at enriching the content of this article.*

Keywords: *nature, ecological culture, man, living creature, ecology, forces of nature.*

Nature is sacred meat for all living beings on earth. Nature feeds them, clothes them, protects them from heat and cold. In turn, living creatures love nature. This love can be considered real only if it can be combined with the feeling of protecting nature and increasing its wealth. In the recent past, we pretended that we love nature, but we forgot that we are responsible for its preservation. This irresponsibility created the ground for a new science known as «Ecology».

The word "Ecology" is derived from the words "eko" - home, dwelling, "logos" - science, teaching, and it refers to environmental degradation and the factors that cause it, prevention of environmental destruction. explores the basics of promoting knowledge about the development of measures.

It is the need of the hour for a mature person of the new century to be able to show the elements of ecological culture. Ecological culture is an in-depth knowledge of the environment, a sense of protecting nature, caring for plants and animals, rational use of natural resources, and their reproduction. is a high indicator of practical activity aimed at grieving. A person who can reflect these qualities can be called the owner of ecological culture.

Do not allow excess water from consumption to flow from the taps, do not pollute water bodies, do not throw garbage wherever you encounter it, keep the dwellings tidy, do not break plants and flowers and plant them, care for animals The simplest manifestations of ecological civilization are actions such as making, taking care of birds, and turning houses and alleys into flower beds.

In the current period, there is an imbalance between man and nature, scientific and technical development and the environment, society and ecology. All of this puts a cross over the issue of further improvement of ecological culture.

It is known that everything in nature is harmonious. And the person who makes good use of scientific and technical achievements breaks this harmony and treats him cruelly. Improper use of natural resources: water, land has changed the ecology. Incorrect planning of agricultural crops, excessive use of chemical fertilizers have a negative impact on soil fertility and human health. Pollution of water bodies by the toxic effluents flowing from the enterprises, first of all, causes a disaster to the animal world and the world of plants. The smoke and gas coming out of vehicles spoils the air quality. All this requires ecological culture from a person.

In fact, ecological culture begins with feeling and loving nature with all its beauty. Man's victory over the forces of nature - cold and heat, drought, fires, various disasters - changes his attitude towards it. This blindness gradually turns into a conscious attitude. The feeling of love for nature is rich, and the attitude towards it is an integral part of personal culture.

Everyone can enjoy nature. But this does not mean love for nature. Love for nature begins with understanding it, realizing its beauties, starting a relationship with nature.

On the other hand, nature nurtures such feelings as observation, sensitivity, femininity in a person. It is manifested in two ways: in the relationship to nature and to oneself.

A person learns not only to enjoy nature, but also to understand it well. As a result, feeling his identity, he tries to find the "thing" from nature that allowed him to become a human being, i.e., human cultural feelings. So, human feelings are nourished by looking at nature with love.

Nature awakens a sense of homeland in a person, encourages him to work and courage, perfects many feelings and demands many things. For a cultured, spiritually mature person, protecting the nature of his Motherland becomes an integral part of his life and work.

Man is the only living creature on Earth, and he is responsible for the destruction of nature. This is due to our tendency to overuse the natural resources of our planet. As a result, there will be changes in the climate due to global warming, pollution and deforestation.

Climate change was not so clear about 50 years ago. However, with the development of technology and the increasing dependence of people on various goods, they have become significant.

The increase in the population of the planet, the desire for a luxurious life and the constant need for the development of technology have a negative impact on the environment. In addition, there are some factors that regularly affect nature:

Agriculture.

The environmental impact of agriculture varies across the spectrum of agricultural practices around the world. Ultimately, the impact on the environment depends on the farming system used by farmers. The impact of agriculture on the nature of the world is related to many factors and depends on the diversity of soil, water, air, flora and fauna. Some of the environmental problems associated with agriculture include: climate change, deforestation, irrigation problems, pollution, soil degradation, etc.

Introduction and invasive species.

The introduction of species into new areas by any means and for any reason has led to large and permanent changes in nature. Rats, cats and goats have changed the biodiversity of many islands. In addition, the introduction caused genetic changes in the local fauna, where interbreeding occurred.

Energy industry.

Energy has many environmental impacts. Energy has been used by humans for thousands of years, beginning with the use of fire for light, heat, cooking, and protection. Consumption of fossil fuel resources leads to global warming and climate change. In most parts of the world, little is being done to slow these changes. If more research is done on the use of viable alternative energy sources, our impact on nature may be less hostile.

Pollution.

Humans pollute many natural objects, including air, water, soil, and more. This is due to many human activities such as transportation, electricity generation, waste disposal, agricultural land pollution, etc. Pollution is harmful not only to humans, but also to animals and plants. We can see many species of flora and fauna disappearing from the face of the Earth.

Technologies.

Although technologies make human life easier and more convenient, they also pose a great threat to nature, which is pollution, radiation risk, use of natural resources, etc.

Deforestation in the world.

Deforestation and large-scale destruction of forest resources for the purpose of increasing the area of agricultural land or urbanization have a profound effect on the environment. Thus, there is exploitation of nature and the environment beyond safe limits. As a result, wild animals enter settlements and attack people. Deforestation reduces the area of forests and threatens the life of wild species.

Overuse of goods.

Humanity consumes more goods than necessary. People tend to own hundreds of pairs of leather shoes, wallets, belts, etc. All these items are made of leather and animal skins. Many wild animals are slaughtered not for meat, but for by-products. Thus, the unbridled desire for goods actually causes great pain and suffering in ordinary animals. Even tigers and elephants were killed in large numbers for their skins and tusks.

Artificial light.

Artificial light at night is one of the most obvious physical changes humans have made to the biosphere, and is the simplest form of pollution that can be observed from space. The main impact of artificial lighting on nature is related to the use of light as a source of information (not a source of energy).

Hunting efficiency of visual predators is usually increased by artificial lighting, changing the location of animals in the food chain. Artificial light also affects animal orientation, migration, and hormone levels, which can disrupt circadian rhythms.

Mining.

The impact of mining operations on nature leads to erosion, formation of sinkholes, loss of biological diversity, contamination of soil, underground and surface water with chemicals during mining. In addition to harming the environment, the pollution of the leaking chemicals also affects the health of the local population.

Transportation.

The environmental impact of transportation is significant because it is a major consumer of energy and burns most of the world's oil. It causes air pollution, including nitrogen oxides and particulate matter, and is a significant contributor to global warming through carbon dioxide emissions.

The factors listed on the basis of this specific information prompted us to make the following conclusion regarding its impact on nature and ecology: we also leave our attitude to it, that is, our ecological culture. Ecological culture means not only not to harm nature, but also to contribute to its recovery, beautification, and prosperity, and to fight fiercely against those who destroy the environment.

REFERENCES

1. Alimova M. I., Egamberdiev N. B., THE ROLE OF SCIENCE FROM CHILDHOOD AS A CASE STUDY THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN. SCIENCE AND INNOVATION INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL VOLUME 2 ISSUE 1 JANUARY 2023. 26-34p.

2. Alimova Madinaxon Iskanqar qizi, Egamberdiev N.B, UZBEK WOMEN IN DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENCE. SCIENCE AND INNOVATION INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL VOLUME 2 ISSUE 1 JANUARY 2023. 17-25-p.
3. Dilshoda Jalilova Ural qizi. BO‘LAJAK BOSHLANG‘ICH SINFI O‘QITUVCHILARIDA AXBOROT KOMPETENTLIGINI RIVOJLANTIRISH MASALASINING AHAMIYATI. RAQAMLI TEXNOLOGIYALAR DAVRIDA TILLARNI INTENSIV O‘QITISHNING PSIXOLOGIK- PEDAGOGIK JIHLTLARI RESPUBLIKA ILMIY-AMALIY ANJUMANI. 2023-yil 2-iyun (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7993607>)
4. Dilshoda Jalilova Ural qizi, Shahzoda Jamilova. BO‘LAJAK BOSHLANG‘ICH SINFI O‘QITUVCHILARINI INNOVATSION FAOLIYATGA TAYYORLASHNING E‘TIBORLI JIHLTLARI. YANGILANAYOTGAN O‘ZBEKISTON TARAQQIYOTIDA IQTISODIY FANLARNI O‘QITISHNING DOLZARB MASALALARI mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy-amaliy konferensiyasi. 2023-yil 16-iyun. https://scholar.google.com/scholar?hl=en&as_sdt=0%2C5&q=%222181-3337
5. Jalilova D.U. Psychological And Technological Features of Increasing the Efficiency of Educational Activity of Talented Students in Presidential Schools. Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices ISSN NO: 2770-2367 (<https://zienjournals.com>).
6. Madinaxon Alimova Iskandar qizi. WASTEWATER POLLUTION AND ITS EFFECTS ON HUMAN HEALTH. «ҚИШЛОҚ ВА СУВ ХЎЖАЛИГИНИНГ ЗАМОНАВИЙ МУАММОЛАРИ» *мавзусидаги анъанавий XXII – ёш олимлар*, www.tiiame.uz магистрантлар ва иқтидорли талабаларнинг илмий-амалий анжумани. Тошкент - 2023 йил www.tiiame.uz
7. Madinaxon Alimova Iskandar qizi, Egamberdiev N.B. BIOCHEMICAL BASIS OF THE BIOLOGICAL TREATMENT METHOD IN WASTE CLEANING OF WATERS. SCIENCE AND INNOVATION INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL VOLUME 2 ISSUE 5 MAY 2023 UIF-2022: 8.2 | ISSN: 2181-3337 | SCIENTISTS.UZ
8. Madinaxon Alimova Iskandar qizi, Egamberdiev N.B. THE IMPORTANCE OF SCIENCE AND EDUCATION IN DEVELOPING DESIGN ABILITY IN PRESCHOOL AND PRIMARY SCHOOL CHILDREN. SCIENCE AND INNOVATION INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL VOLUME 2 ISSUE 4 APRIL 2023. 566-569p.
9. Madinaxon Alimova Iskandar qizi, Egamberdiev N.B. WOMEN IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF SCIENCE AND EDUCATION IN UZBEKISTAN: OPPORTUNITIES AND PROSPECTS. SCIENCE AND INNOVATION INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL VOLUME 2 ISSUE 4 APRIL 2023. 451-452-453p.